

MEASUREMENT OF THE MAGNETIC FIELD INDUCTION MODULE IN THE AREA OF THE AKADEMIK VERNADSKY STATION DURING THE 29TH SEASONAL UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC EXPEDITION

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One of the main objectives of the State Program for Antarctic Research is to study the geological structure of West Antarctica. Using tectonomagnetic and magnetovariational monitoring in the area of the Akademik Vernadsky Antarctic station, the modern geodynamics of the Antarctic Peninsula are being investigated. For these studies, a tectonomagnetic polygon was established in the early 21st century, consisting of observation points located near active tectonic faults. Measuring the magnetic induction module at the polygon points and conducting profile measurements makes it possible to build maps of the geomagnetic field induction. Developing such maps for different epochs allows researchers to assess changes in the geomagnetic field, which are mainly associated with processes in the Earth's lithosphere.

During the 29th seasonal Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition (UAE), magnetic field induction module measurements were taken at tectonomagnetic polygon points using a GSM-19G magnetometer/gradiometer. For the first time, measurements at these points were conducted using a gradiometer, which allows immediate identification of whether a point is located in a positive or negative anomaly area and to estimate the gradient of the geomagnetic field induction at that point.

Profile measurements of the magnetic field induction module were also conducted in the vicinity of the Akademik Vernadsky station. For this purpose, a sensor and electronics unit were mounted on the boat's bow. Measurements were taken using the GSM-19G device in magnetometer mode. The device is equipped with a GPS antenna mounted near the sensor, allowing accurate location tracking for each measurement. The boat's speed and measurement intervals were selected to ensure that the distance between adjacent points was within 10–12 meters. This enables the creation of a detailed map of the geomagnetic field induction in the selected observation area.

To exclude the variation component of the geomagnetic field, measurements conducted at polygon points and along profiles should be synchronized with recordings from the "Argentine Islands" geomagnetic observatory (code AIA) at the Ukrainian Antarctic Station. In 2024, a GSM-90 magnetometer was installed at the AIA observatory. The measurement interval of this device is 1 second. This enables the acquisition of synchronous data and the removal of the variation component from the measurements performed at the polygon points and along the profiles.